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AGR3 activation during metastasis to the lung.

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Citations

1. Delom, F., Mohtar, M.A., Hupp, T. and Fessart, D., 2020. The anterior gradient-2 interactome. American Journal of Physiology-Cell Physiology, 318(1), pp.C40-C47.
2. Barraclough, D.L., Platt-Higgins, A., de Silva Rudland, S., Barraclough, R., Winstanley, J., West, C.R. and Rudland, P.S., 2009. The metastasis-associated anterior gradient 2 protein is correlated with poor survival of breast cancer patients. The American journal of pathology, 175(5), pp.1848-1857.